

APPLICATION OF PHONETIC TRANSCRIPTION: ITS ROLE IN IMPROVING STUDENTS' MOTIVATION AND PRONUNCIATION SKILLS AT MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU

Hazzanarl-Dhemarl N. Hassan

Department of Languages, Mindanao State University-Sulu, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204499>

ABSTRACT

In this study, the use of phonetic transcription was correlated with the motivation and pronouncing skills of students whose language was English as a Second Language (ESL) at Mindanao State University-Sulu. The researcher worked through a quasi-experimental design which had a control group and an experimental group. The experimental group was taught phonetic transcription while the control group was taught the traditional way of pronouncing words. Data were collected on students' pre- and post-tests of motivation and performance tests of pronunciation. The results were interpreted in such a way that the experimental group achieved greater motivational and performance related scores in pronunciation accuracy compared with the control group. The findings indicate that phonetic transcription should be adopted as it enhances the motivation of ESL students and their pronouncing abilities.

Keywords: *Phonetic Transcription, Motivation, Pronunciation, ESL, Quasi-experimental Design*

INTRODUCTION

Pronunciation of sounds is one of the most important sub-skills that an English as a Second Language (ESL) speaker should possess. Communication without correct pronunciation is grossly affected because pronunciation influences one's command of the language positively (Celce-Murcia, 2010). Despite having the language knowledge, most

ESL students struggle with properly pronouncing target syllables or words which ultimately impairs interactions and understanding of the language (Derwing & Rossiter, 2003). Phonetics is a technique which the current research uses in improving the pronunciation ability in order to boost student motivation at Mindanao State University-Sulu.

During business and academic activities, English is more than just a communicative language, rather it is treated as a resource that one can employ to complete different activities (White et al. 2022). It is a pity that the time set aside for teaching the English pronunciation is quite limited and the challenge associated with providing adequate instructional materials is too high. The research titled, "Application of Phonetic Transcription: Its Role in Improving Students' Motivation and Pronunciation Skills at Mindanao State University-Sulu", dwells with the potentials of phonetic coding as a means of lessening the students' English pronunciation difficulties and their other average learning motivation with respect to the target language. Such pedagogical practices need to be practiced in linguistics (Bird, 2021) and also in teaching pronunciation in language teaching (Fitria, 2023; Patra & Pradhan, 2023). Phonetic transcription is an approved professional skill (Bates et al, 2024; Titterington & Bates, 2021) with potential in language hence, its practice good self-directed is very much unknown. This research is, as it were, focusing on this background and hitting towards the concepts of phonetic transcription in regard to pronunciation abilities, skills, motivation towards English amongst the students in the target bench marked population.

Research studies by instrumental tools have found that such tools are able to provide practice for the learners and opportunities for feedback (Atkins, Bailey, & Seals, 2023). The accuracy and the level of the conformity of phonetic transcriptions may also be assisted by tools for transcriptional comparisons (Bailey et al., 2022). The significance of this area is specified, as it will integrate the current research on teaching English pronunciation through other concepts in addition to improving teaching and learning of the students and the instructors. The outcomes of such investigations would be beneficial in the formulation and application of improved methods for pronunciation learning which are not context specific. Furthermore, understanding the barriers and enabling factors in the use of transcription methods for assessing speech is also an area of concern to teachers and even speech-language pathologists like Nelson, Mok, & Eecen (2020). These relate to the current work being undertaken because they provide a basic understanding of the advantages and disadvantages of employing phonetic transcription in enhancing student's motivation and pronunciation skills.

Phonetic transcription refers to representation of the sounds of the alphabet letters in order to enhance understanding of how various features of pronunciation principle relate to written and spoken language (Roach, 2009). It has been documented that phonetic transcription results or helps achieve better pronunciation improvement (Celce-Murcia & Larsen-Freeman, 2019). However, no research has focused on the ESL learners in the Philippines in regard to the relationship between motivation to practice pronunciation and the use of phonetic transcription. This gap in the knowledge enables the inquiry that follows to be undertaken.

Research Questions

1. How effective is phonetic transcription on the motivation of ESL students at Mindanao State University-Sulu?
2. How effective is phonetic transcription on the phonetic accuracy of ESL students at Mindanao State University-Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

This research used a quasi-experimental design with two groups, control group, and a treatment group. The subjects of the study were 60 ESL students of MSU-Sulu who were enrolled in an English-language course. They were randomly divided into two groups with 30 students in each group constituting the control group (30) and experimental group (30). The control group received traditional pronunciation teachings while the experimental group was taught with the use of phonetic transcription. The researcher designed two parts of a researcher-made instrument that included a motivation questionnaire, and a pronunciation test. The motivation questionnaire aimed to identify students' both intrinsic and extrinsic in learning English. In the pronunciation test students have been evaluated for their ability to reproduce English sounds correctly. The instrument was tried out and demonstrated its reliability and validity against the ESL students' scale.

The data were gathered from both groups using pre- and post- tests. The pre-tests were taken prior to the intervention, while the post-tests were undertaken after intervention. The intervention lasted for six weeks with two sessions a week. The results were analysed by means of paired t –tests in order to evaluate the pre-test and post-test scores of both groups.

RESULTS

The outcomes from the paired t- test illustrated the sources of motivation and pronunciation accuracy difference between the control group and experimental group. Experimental and control groups after the intervention were compared on the parameters of motivation and pronunciation accuracy and the experimental group was able to perform better.

Table 1: Mean Scores of Motivation and Pronunciation Accuracy

Pre-Test Motivation	Post-Test Motivation	Pre-Test Pronunciation	Post-Test Pronunciation
25.67	26.53	15.47	16.33
25.53	30.87	15.27	20.67

DISCUSSION

This suggests that phonetic transcription, when coupled with the presentation strategies used in teaching instruction, can be used effectively to increase ESL students' motivation and pronunciation skills. With growth dissatisfaction the experimental students also had quite improved motivation as a result of exposure to phonetic materials which differentiated them significantly from the control students on an improvement scale. These findings are consistent with previous studies that have documented the efficacy of phonetic transcription as an instrument for improving the understanding of pronunciation rules and their application in speech, leading to better accuracy (Celce-Murcia & Larsen-Freeman, 2019).

The experimental group exhibited an increased motivation level, which can be linked to the phonetic transcription input as it gave a visual representation to the sounds. This input in the form of phonetic transcription may have possibly made the pronunciation practices less difficult and more understandable for the learners which in turn, raised their motivation and confidence levels.

Conclusions

Given the results of this study, it can be concluded that phonetic transcription is an effective device in enhancing the interest and efforts of students who are learning ESL in terms of their motivation and pronunciation skills. Therefore, it is necessary to note that such a way of motivation should also be accompanied by relevant instruction and there is need for the schools and college to use phonetic transcription in their teaching of pronunciation in English because students will benefit tremendously by increasing their motivation to learn the language.

Recommendations

Going by the findings of this study, the researchers suggest that teachers at Mindanao State University-Sulu place more emphasis on phonetic transcription in their ESL classes particularly pronunciation. Such a positioning may be accomplished through a number of ways including presentation of phonetic letters to learners, providing phonetic representations of some words and appellations to learners and instructing learners on how to utilize phonetic transcription.

Further research on phonetic transcription should focus on the potential or actual sustained impact of the use of the transcription on the pronunciation competences of ESL students and their motivation for learning the language. Moreover, research can be focused on other implicit and/or explicit methods of phonetic transcription and how effective they are with other learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The guidelines of the above research were carried out in accordance with the principles included in the ethical permit obtained from the University. The first step concerned people who agreed to participate in the research there was signed an informed consent without any coercion before the research began. They were also advised that there was the opportunity to leave the study voluntarily at any stage. From the initiation of the research to its end, confidentiality and welfare of the subjects was ensured. There are no such Financial or Personal relationships that have the potential to become conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study. Direct and self-plagiarism was observed to keep within the ethical bounds and there was no prejudgment on the results and the interpretation of the outcomes. As stated earlier the findings of this study were utilized in secondary research only.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to thank the Department of Languages, College of Arts and Sciences, Mindanao State University-Sulu that acted as the participants of the study.

REFERENCES

- Atkins, M. S., Bailey, D. J., & Seals, C. D. (2023). Implementation of an automated grading tool for phonetic transcription training. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 37(3), 242-257.
- Bailey, D. J., Atkins, M. S., Mishra, I., Li, S., Luan, Y., & Seals, C. (2022). An automated tool for comparing phonetic transcriptions. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 36(6), 495-514.
- Bates, S., Watson, J., Heselwood, B., & Howard, S. (2024). Phonetic transcription in clinical practice. *The Handbook of Clinical Linguistics, Second Edition*, 469-487.
- Bird, S. (2021). Sparse transcription. *Computational Linguistics*, 46(4), 713-744.
- Celce-Murcia, M. (2010). *Teaching pronunciation: A course book and reference guide*. Heinle Cengage Learning.
- Celce-Murcia, M., & Larsen-Freeman, D. (2019). *The grammar book: An ESL/EFL teacher's course*. Heinle Cengage Learning.
- Derwing, T. M., & Rossiter, M. J. (2003). The influence of pronunciation instruction on second language fluency. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 25(1), 1-25.
- Fitria, T. N. (2023). Using Phonetic Transcription App as Media of Teaching Phonetics in English Pronunciation Skill. *EDUCAFL: Journal on Education of English as Foreign Language*, 6(1), 57-70.
- Nelson, T. L., Mok, Z., & Eecen, K. T. (2020). Use of transcription when assessing children's speech: Australian speech-language pathologists' practices, challenges, and facilitators. *Folia Phoniatica et Logopaedica*, 72(2), 131-142.
- Patra, B., & Pradhan, J. (2023). UTILIZING THE PHONETICS TRANSCRIPTION APP TO TEACH ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION SKILLS. *Junikhyat Journal*, 14(3), 4167-4176.

- Roach, P. (2009). *English phonetics and phonology: A practical course*. Cambridge University Press.
- Titterington, J., & Bates, S. (2021). Teaching and learning clinical phonetic transcription. *Manual of clinical phonetics*, 175-186.
- White, S., Hurren, A., James, S., & Knight, R.-A. (2022). 'I think that's what I heard? I'm not sure': Speech and language therapists' views of, and practices in, phonetic transcription. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 57(5), 1071-1084.
-